

Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data (DyMoN)

Policy briefing

DyMoN project, January 2024

Cities are challenged to effectively contribute to climate and environmental targets regarding CO₂ emissions, air quality, pollutants, and noise from urban mobility. The DyMoN project proposes that cities use digital nudging to promote more sustainable mobility of citizens (i.e., walk, cycle, public transport). The project developed and trialled a novel approach of such nudging that applies behaviour change techniques in combination with situation awareness. Such awareness considers the users' proximity to cycling routes, public transport stops, traffic situation, weather forecast, and other available data. The DyMoN recommendations concern city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical issues. Stakeholders in sustainable mobility addressed are city policy makers, managers of mobility infrastructure and services, providers of other services (e.g., behavioural intervention methods, ICT and data services), and citizens who use such services.

Introduction

Cities face the challenge of promoting sustainable mobility to reduce CO₂ emissions, improve air quality, avoid pollutants and noise, and thereby make the city a more liveable place. A core objective is to enable and encourage the necessary shift from using fossil-fuel vehicles towards more sustainable mobility modes, i.e., walking, cycling, using public transport. To achieve this, cities can use "hard" measures such as congestion charges, car-free streets and removal of parking space or apply "soft" methods of nudging to steer citizens towards voluntarily changing their mobility behaviours.

The high use of mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and increasing familiarity of citizens with mobile applications allow using digital nudging methods to motivate citizens to adopt sustainable mobility behaviours. The behaviour change intervention of digital nudging is a relatively low-cost method while avoiding political issues associated with unpopular "hard" measures. However, use of digital nudging to shift mobility mode choice towards "green" options requires sufficient sustainable mobility infrastructure and services to be appropriate.

The DyMoN approach of situation-aware nudging

Digital nudging has been proposed for promoting sustainable behaviours in different fields, including urban mobility. Various behaviour change techniques have already been applied, e.g., informational campaigns, social norms, mobility challenges and other game-like methods, among others. The DyMoN project developed and trialled an innovative approach that allows using such methods in combination with situation awareness. The approach takes account of the fact that the situation in which a nudge reaches a person can be crucial for a successful behavioural

intervention. Regarding the promotion of sustainable mobility choices situational factors, for example, include weather, traffic situation, proximity to public transport stations or cycling routes.

DyMoN created a “Nudging Repository”, a set of 166 different nudges that are characterized by mobility mode (walk, cycle, public transport), trip purpose (leisure, commuting), behaviour change technique, situational factors, nudge text, timing, and general use (when a nudge can also be used not linked to specific situational data). The behaviour change techniques include action planning (e.g., a sustainable mobility trip), information about consequences (e.g., positive health or environmental effects), social comparison (e.g., information on what others do), prompts/cues (e.g., reminders to keep using sustainable mobility modes), among others.

To enable situation awareness, DyMoN has brought together in a “Data Hub” various data on situational factors as mentioned above. The “Data Hub” allows connecting the current GPS location information of users of a smartphone app with such data that define their immediate situation. Based on the identified situation and user preferences regarding sustainable mobility mode/s the DyMoN system can select appropriate nudges from the Nudging Repository and send these situation-aware notifications to the users of the smartphone app.

A tendency in digital nudging has been trying to collect ever more data about the users and their mobility behaviour via their smartphones to possibly improve the nudging through user tracking and profiling. Instead, the DyMoN approach uses situational factors external to the user to support sustainable mobility choices while minimizing the demand for personal data. The key data the DyMoN system needs for providing nudges is a user’s sustainable mobility preferences and location when connecting with the system. But this data is deleted after sending the nudge notifications, i.e., there is no tracking or profiling of the user’s mobility behaviour.

The DyMoN approach has been successfully applied in a functional proof-of-concept and in a pilot demonstration with commuters in the City of Salzburg.

DyMoN recommendations

The DyMoN policy recommendations are based on a review of the literature on related topics and the project’s own empirical research and experiences. The recommendations focus on the topics of city policies and plans for sustainable mobility, behaviour change methods for promoting use of sustainable mobility modes, supporting ICT and data services, and related legal and ethical issues. Stakeholders in sustainable mobility addressed are city policy makers, managers of mobility infrastructure and services, providers of other services (e.g., behavioural intervention methods, ICT and data services), and citizens who use such services.

Sustainable urban mobility policies and plans

- Rec. 1: Embed and strengthen sustainable mobility in city mobility policies and plans
- Rec. 2: Ensure appropriate involvement of citizens, local businesses and civil society organisations
- Rec. 3: Give special attention to active mobility to achieve environmental and health benefits
- Rec. 4: Combine improvements of sustainable mobility infrastructure and services with behaviour change methods to promote their usage

Behaviour change methods for sustainable mobility

- Rec. 5: Use behavioural interventions to advance the shift towards sustainable mobility
- Rec. 6: Select appropriate digital nudging methods for city sustainable mobility initiatives

- Rec. 7: Highlight positive effects of sustainable mobility for the individual citizen and the community

ICT and data services for behaviour change

- Rec. 8: Use ICT-based services for digital nudging of sustainable mobility behaviour
- Rec. 9: Take account of what citizens expect from an application that supports sustainable mobility behaviour
- Rec. 10: Make clear to the users who is responsible for the digital nudging service and city information and physical services
- Rec. 11: Improve the availability and access to data required for supporting sustainable mobility plans and behaviour change initiatives

Legal and ethical aspects

- Rec. 12: Ensure full compliance of the digital services with personal data protection regulations
- Rec. 13: Implement personal data protection by design and by default
- Rec. 14: Involve citizens in the design of appropriate digital nudges
- Rec. 15: Use only behaviour change methods that are acceptable in the context of public policy and services

Detailed thematic background of the recommendations is given in a project deliverable (see below DyMoN 2024).

Project identity

Project name: Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data (DyMoN)

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Consortium: Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH, Salzburg, Austria – project coordinator

University of Salzburg, Department of Geoinformatics, Austria

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Further reading: DyMoN (2024). Evaluation of pilot demonstrations and policy recommendations & briefing. Project Deliverable D2.2a, January 2024. Available in Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/communities/dymon/>

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